
Representing the Knowledge Domains that Characterise Cyber-Physical Systems

A positioning white paper for CPS in relation to the HiPEAC Vision 2026

Cyber-physical Systems (CPS) are composite technologies, that is they are composed of many contributing technologies, representing large-scale complex and safety-critical systems. The significance of this classification is important. From the research perspective it provides a focus on the cross-cutting multi-dimensional challenges related to combining technology domains for real world interactions. This fundamentally facilitates technology integration, supports technology transfer of contributing domains, and ultimately market creation. The HiPEAC Next Computing Paradigm (NCP) expects to include interactions in the real world, where CPS research advances will boost this capacity and reciprocally, the NCP provides technology integrations and orchestration important for cyber-physical systems.

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Today, there are many technology domains involved with the creation of large-scale safety-critical systems, which are used in sectors including transport, health, robotics, manufacturing. In the longer term these will be in the home, where miniaturization will play a role. These applications have the encompassing term of cyber-physical systems (CPS), providing integrations of many contributing technology domains. Mastery of the digital to real world boundary opens up increasingly new means of value generation by CPS, which will be greatly aided by NCP infrastructure with computing as a backbone, already encompassing great advances in connectivity (including IoT, Big Data), pattern recognition and decision making (AI). At the same time, the integration concerns typical in the realm of CPS, including certified dependability, energy management and real-time capacities, will become pervasive for NCP and tomorrow's systems.

In this article we explain that research and engineering for future CPS needs a centre of gravity in order to draw the associated communities closer together. This will provide common goals around which technical advances can be aligned. Overviews of the domains involved are provided in this article, with examples of their relevance in the creation of CPS and to some common challenges.

Aggregating diverse technologies are multi-dimensional challenges, with many influencing dependencies across the contributing technology domains, especially at higher levels where the whole system is drawn together. This means that, to make good progress, Europe will require new forms of coordination in order to orchestrate research and to capitalize on lessons learned related to the cumulative advances between the community research domains.

Key insights

- Large-scale safety-critical systems encompass a common perspective of what is classed as cyber-physical systems. These CPS are physically interactive (high certification obligation) and increasingly collaborative (task sharing). They involve many contributor and influencer technology domains in their creation, who each tend to make advances in isolation. *Creating the technical bridges between these domains to channel technology development is essential for future CPS.*
- The scope for bridging the technology domains is wide and they need technical interfaces around which to align. Discussions have indicated self-alignment of these groups is needed through *centres of gravity, particularly on the topic of real-time safe and secure automation.*
- *A new form of research coordination is necessary to direct cumulative integrated developments from the stakeholder communities.* Furthermore CPS projects should advance technologies for research interactions alongside technologies for the system.
- The development of CPS requires a holistic approach, guided by target products, that brings together a wide range of disciplines. These should include not only functional, system and enabling technologies, but also production line, policy and society, and fields like psychology, sociology and ethnography, among others.

- Aggregating, or system technologies, have different and much longer industrial uptake lifecycles than specific parts or component technologies. Research programmes mostly treat them the same and both technology types suffer. *A dedicated team* from the research programmes *would be very beneficial for investigating and implementing new technical capacities for multi-stakeholder complex group research.*
- CPS represent a significant part of national infrastructures and where lie some of the most devious and complex research integration challenges to be solved. Infrastructure represents an important means of market capture and thus sovereignty, whilst system architecture is a determining factor of technology uptake and the green transition. National funding for infrastructure stability and adaptability, particularly investing in system thinking/interdisciplinarity will play a critical role for Europe on the world stage. This is not only in terms of economic stability and productivity but also moving to a culture that ensures also a functioning natural world for future generations.
- Artificial Intelligence (AI) has become operational and regulated, with EU AI Act obligations for high-risk CPS applications expected from 2026. This demands a shift from "trustworthy AI" to "assured AI in context"; domain-specific assurance integrated with existing safety certification. Critical challenges include AI change management (controlled lifecycle processes for updates/retraining), stakeholder-differentiated explainability, and human-AI teaming assurance. Collaboration between AI, CPS engineering, and regulatory communities is essential to establish shared certification pathways.

Introduction and new cross-domain development approaches

In order to manage large complex problems, people break them down into parts. It is for this reason that, from the technology point of view, there are many contributing and influencing domains involved in the creation of future safety-critical products. Of course, the parts subsequently need to be assembled together in order to address the initial complex problem. For the same reasons, the various technological contributions for future large-scale safety-critical systems require layered aggregation in order to achieve these physically interactive and collaborating systems.

This creates significant, multi-dimensional influences across CPS communities, directly affecting our ability to industrialise technology. Part of this challenge lies in assuring CPS, which should be based on sound methods of justifying they are fit for purpose and that all usage risks are adequately addressed, notwithstanding the complexity and the heterogeneity of the CPS components and of the communities of stakeholders involved. Assurance alone, historically has relied heavily on *expert judgement* and this worked. Recently the complexity of the CPS that we try to assure as safe has increased very dramatically. In these circumstances, expert judgement based on previous experience alone becomes problematic. The current trend (see Assurance 2.0 [1]) is that we need new methods for building assurance cases which should rely on formal methods and also on *automation* to process complex arguments on which assurance is built.

For the purposes of this article, we take CPS in the context of an application; that is to say, the term could be replaced directly with an example CPS application such as railway transport, an autonomous vehicle, or satellite constellations. In this framing, CPS therefore represent *physically interactive and collaborating systems* that are present in many domains including

transport, health and manufacturing. (For an in-depth definition of CPS, see, for instance, the HiPEAC Vision article “Defining cyber-physical systems: Large-scale safety-critical systems”).

The technology domains involved in CPS, discussed in the subsequent section, range from providers of a) functional properties including sensing, physical action, communication, energy provision, processing and coordinated collaboration to b) system-level engineering including properties like safety and performance specifications, managing customer requirements, architecting, system verification and validation, mechanical engineering and control engineering. There are technology support domains providing c) enabling technology domains like the Internet of Things (IoT), Systems of Systems, Big Data, Artificial Intelligence/machine learning and High-Performance Computing. Finally, there are the influencing domains from d) the production environment, with enterprise processes and product line, and e) the market, such as regulation and current and future needs of society.

These technology domains have tended to transfer technology as a one-to-one mapping with products. However, to respond to the challenges of future CPS and to enhance technology transfer, they will need to take relations with the other contributing domain communities increasingly into account. While the challenges and importance of advancing aggregation techniques are discussed later, there also needs to be a common focal point from which one domain community can interact with any of the other domain communities. This point should provide a common interest based on the physical challenges of these systems. *Discussions have proposed this centre of gravity to be real-time, safe and secure automation of CPS.*

Research on CPS should seek to enhance the interrelations and automation of these three dependability properties, i.e., real-time, safety and security. They are goals that must be achieved at a global level when all the technologies are combined. As an example, each piece of hardware has an impact on the energy consumption of the whole system. Similarly, individual software and hardware components can jeopardize safety if they fail naturally or due to a security breach. These goals can also be variable and related to environmental conditions, such as a train reducing its speed (performance) in response to heavy showers (to maintain safety).

Hence for technologies to be accepted in these systems, they must guarantee these dependability properties, i.e., they must comply with the safety and security constraints of a product in the intended operational environment and not violate the constraints on real-time responses. This means that the easier it is to couple your technology with these system constraints (through automation), the easier it becomes to adjust it to the system - or adjust the system for new technologies.

It can be prohibitively expensive to add new technologies to a CPS as typically re-certification of the whole system is required. Such a challenge can only be treated through having sufficient automated information about the impact of the new technologies on these dependability properties – and particularly the interrelations of those properties. Take systems certified, for instance, against an extreme earthquake occurring every 1000 years (for safety), such as a nuclear plant: in this case, the safety experts currently would prefer no new technologies or patches for security to be added to these systems due to the certification costs.

As a result, historically, interrelations between system properties have been limited to minimize complexity, but the current need for adaptability (to new technologies, to environmental or internal changes) requires this design mindset to be readdressed. So in summary, a centre of gravity, as shown in Figure 1, will provide a useful point to channel us towards more impactful research advances for these future large-scale safety-critical systems.

Figure 1: The stakeholder communities for creating CPS.

While the management of trade-offs between the system properties of performance, safety and security is an established skill in system development, it still remains very much a manual and qualitative process and one that is based on prior experience. It remains a significant bottleneck that holds back the domain communities contributing to CPS.

System-level engineering for CPS is therefore in need of transformative automation. Fortunately, automation between system-level dependability properties can rely on a number of decades of research in techniques¹, some of which have already been applied in industry but are generally in need of new approaches for technology transfer. Such approaches are included in the coordination suggestions for research orchestration described later in this article. Looking forward, AI itself could potentially be leveraged to enable more automated trade-off management and assurance processes for CPS. Machine learning techniques could analyze complex system interrelations, identify optimal trade-off configurations, and support the generation of assurance cases based on operational data. However, any such AI-enabled automation must itself satisfy the assurance requirements now mandated by regulation, including the EU AI Act's provisions for high-risk systems. This creates a recursive challenge: the AI tools used to support CPS assurance must themselves be assured. Realizing this potential will require significant research and collaboration between the AI, CPS engineering, and assurance communities to develop domain-specific AI methodologies that satisfy both functional safety standards (e.g., IEC 61508, ISO 26262, DO-178C) and emerging AI-specific regulations.

Of course, current pressures for industry to find advanced solutions for managing system property trade-offs are also driving the search for automated coupling. As examples of some initiatives, the UK Research Institute in Trustworthy Interconnected Cyber Physical Systems

¹ S. Paul, "D3.4.4. MERgE - Recommendations for Security and Safety Co-engineering v3 partA," 22 April 2016. Online: <https://itea4.org/project/merge.html>. [Accessed 25 Mar. 2026].

(RITICS)² involves dozens of UK universities and industrial collaborators. Topics include safety, security and autonomous systems. Relating to autonomous vehicles, the Intel Research Collaborative Institute of Safety of Autonomous Cars (ICRI-SAVE³), deserves a mention as a vibrant community. Likewise, the VVM project (Verification and Validation Methods, <https://www.vvm-projekt.de/>) built up a sizeable research community addressing the challenges of “safety verification of automated vehicles ... on driving functions up to full automation of vehicles (SAE Level 4 and 5)”.

Many industries are actively looking for solutions to manage the performance, safety and security together, including large enterprise like Siemens, Thales and AVL, who have been forming combined safety-security teams. The challenge also affects small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in their products and services. This challenge is reflected, for example, in the Ada and IEEE conferences, in the IET code of practice on cybersecurity and safety⁴, as well as large research collaborations including MERgE⁵, SeSaMo⁶ and AQUAS⁷, and in co-engineering discussions.

Overview of stakeholder knowledge domains for creating and advancing CPS

There are many stakeholder knowledge domains that contribute to the shaping of cyber-physical systems. We provide here overviews of five key groupings of communities, shown in more detail in Figure 2, which are involved in the creation of CPS. Within the CPS product we have system level and functional level domains, supporting these are the enabling technology domains. Then there are the conditions covered by the production environment domain and the market influencer domains. We provide next descriptions and examples of their relevance to CPS as

Figure 2: Characterising CPS

² "RITICS: Research Institute in Trustworthy Interconnected Cyber-Physical Systems," Online: <https://ritics.org/>. [Accessed 26 Nov. 2023].

³ "ICRI_SAVE," Intel, Online: <https://www.icri-cars.org/>. [Accessed 25 Mar. 2026].

⁴ "IET Code of Practice: Cyber Security and Safety," Institution of Engineering and Technology, Online: <https://electrical.theiet.org/guidance-codes-of-practice/publications-by-category/cyber-security/code-of-practice-cyber-security-and-safety/>. [Accessed 25 Mar. 2026].

⁵ "MERgE: Multi-Concerns Interactions System Engineering," ITEA 4, Online: <https://itea4.org/project/merge.html>. [Accessed 25 Mar. 2026].

⁶ "SESAMO: Security and Safety Modelling on CORDIS," European Commission, Online: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/295354>. [Accessed 25 Mar. 2026].

⁷ "AQUAS: Aggregated Quality Assurance for Systems," Online: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/737475/results>. [Accessed 25 Mar. 2026].

well as their relation to transverse knowledge domain challenges. These include embedded computing as a CPS backbone, system decentralization and decomposability, and physical collaborations with people.

Functional-property domains

CPS functional properties must address aspects that cover sensing, physical action, communication, energy support, processing and coordinated collaboration. Such properties are key characteristics of these systems, with actors in specific communities researching and developing the different components.

The relevance of functional properties becomes more evident when considering novel and innovative advanced applications that are being progressively adopted in several large-scale, safety-critical domains, such as industrial automation, transportation, smart cities, critical infrastructures, space, etc. Some examples can be found in EU-funded projects such as CPSwarm⁸, or Chips Joint Undertaking such as AIDOaRT project⁹ and MATISSE project¹⁰ or Horizon Europe such as MYRTUS Project¹¹ and other CPS cluster initiatives as well as in Horizon Europe SNS projects such as ENVELOPE¹² and AMAZING-6G¹³.

Industry-driven needs and the well-established nature of general research communities in the CPS domain mean that it is feasible to envision projects that might prototype concepts such as swarms of unmanned aerial vehicles and rovers supporting safety and security operations; swarm of unmanned aerial vehicles and possibly ground robots supporting critical infrastructure management; swarms of automated ground robots that collaboratively support humans in logistic operations within a smart warehouse or in last mile delivery operations within a smart city; or enhanced and dynamic platooning applications for autonomous freight vehicles. Currently, the development of such applications cannot leverage a simple plug-and-play integration of the various technologies entailed, given the complexity of managing teams of systems and humans in evolving and dynamic scenarios with emergent properties.

Therefore, to properly combine and integrate the different technology building blocks required, the various 'functional properties communities' have to be properly engaged. Experts from the functional property communities will need to work with other actors with collaborative systems competence. Moreover, while the increased adoption of CPS has resulted in the maturation of solutions for CPS development, a single consistent science for future CPS has not yet been consolidated. Few functional properties community members have already started working alongside other communities on a connective framework e.g., using modelling, design/development tools and methodologies, deployment solutions, monitoring and controlling

⁸ "CPS Swarm," Online: <https://www.cpswarm.eu/> [Accessed 25 Mar. 2026].

⁹ "AIDOaRT," Online: <https://www.aidoart.eu/> [Accessed 16 Jan. 2026].

¹⁰ "MATISSE," Online: <https://matisse-kdt.eu/> [Accessed 16 3 Jan. 2026]

¹¹ "MYRTUS," Online: <https://myrtus-project.eu/> [Accessed 16 Jan. 2026].

¹² "ENVELOPE," Online: <https://envelope-project.eu/> [Accessed 25 Mar. 2026].

¹³ "AMAZING-6G," Online: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101192035> [Accessed 25 Mar. 2026].

solutions for large-scale challenges. In this context, model-centric approaches have clear relevance for facilitating collaboration between experts from different sectors and thus enabling the definition, composition, verification and simulation of collaborative, autonomous CPS.

For these reasons, it is important for future CPS to be considered not only from the technology perspective but also as an application domain where the technology of the functional property communities plays a role for aggregation of CPS-related research. To promote this, closer and wider collaboration is needed within the communities, along with new research initiatives. Understanding the nature of this aggregation from the bottom up and top down is important for driving the communities towards much-needed technology advances. The resulting collaboration plays a very important role in finding solutions to the bottlenecks that currently prevent CPS from having greater impact on society; such solutions would also promote market uptake, open new markets and optimize the use of resources in the various industry sectors.

In this context, each functional property community contributes distinct but tightly interdependent capabilities.

Sensing. Advanced sensing technologies (e.g., LiDAR, radar, vision, inertial and distributed sensor systems) enable CPS to achieve high-fidelity, timely and context-aware perception of the physical world. Emerging paradigms such as event-driven, collaborative and quantum-enhanced sensing are increasingly adopted in response to the specific constraints and requirements of safety-critical application domains.

Physical action. Actuation technologies, including mechatronic systems and advanced control interfaces, translate higher-level decisions into safe, precise and predictable physical actions under real-time constraints. Emerging trends such as soft robotics, adaptive control and human-aware actuation are increasingly relevant in safety-critical CPS domains.

Communication. Advanced communication technologies, with the evolution from 5G towards beyond-5G and 6G being particularly relevant for safety-critical CPS, enable ultra-reliable and low-latency connectivity, network slicing, and integration across the edge–cloud continuum. Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC) is also emerging as a key trend, creating new technological bridges between communication and sensing.

Energy support. Energy provision technologies, including power generation, storage and intelligent power management, underpin the autonomy and operational continuity of CPS. Emerging trends such as advanced battery technologies, hybrid energy architectures and energy-aware management support increasingly demanding CPS applications across diverse operational contexts.

Processing. Processing technologies, from embedded multicore platforms to edge and cloud computing architectures, enable real-time data interpretation and complex decision-making in CPS. The increasing distribution of processing across the edge–cloud continuum improves scalability and performance, but complicates timing guarantees and system dependability.

Coordinated collaboration. Coordinated collaboration technologies, including distributed coordination protocols and multi-agent approaches, enable teams of CPS, potentially extended to include humans-in-the-loop, to achieve collective goals under decentralization and emergent

behaviours. Distributed intelligence and distributed AI are emerging as key trends shaping future collaborative CPS.

These communities have many cross-cutting challenges for future CPS. Embedded computing will evolve significantly, playing an essential enabling role for functional properties. For instance, the need to use specific sensors on a CPS and to timely process the relevant raw data onboard will need increased computational power. However, energy limitations introduce other constraints; only a holistic vision of CPS can help drive research initiatives. Moreover, the envisioned combination of 5G, beyond 5G and Smart Networks and Services/6G technologies with distributed and high-performance computing will pave the way towards a deep integration of future CPS in the computing continuum, where there are also direct links with enabling technologies, discussed presently, such as IoT and Systems of Systems. In relation to decentralization and decomposability, with distributed intelligence and emergent properties, an example research context would aim to solve/work on delays in physical, computing and actuation timing. This requires model design and simulation approaches to capture the full heterogeneity of the system and its contributing communities. Physical interaction with people requires a system to have high fidelity knowledge of its environment and its physical dynamics. This requires the technologies of the functional properties community, which in turn need integration with the safety and security measures set by the system-engineering community. In the future, achieving greater energy efficiency will pose an additional challenge for CPS. The evolution of CPS must consider their overall energy footprint to minimize their environmental impact. To achieve this goal, all aspects, components, and technologies related to CPS need to be carefully considered. This effort will involve traceability among the contributing communities. It is therefore evident that the best way to advance future CPS is to further support integration and aggregation approaches for community collaboration.

[Systems-engineering domains](#)

The development of CPS requires a holistic development approach that brings together a wide range of disciplines. This includes the typical systems engineering disciplines, such as requirements engineering, architectural design, implementation and quality assurance including system-wide responsiveness, safety and security. The disciplines of this community are important in terms of both the CPS in general and individual systems engineering sub-processes, such as mechanical engineering, control theory, electrical engineering and software engineering.

In almost all of our application-driven future scenarios, like in autonomous driving and Industry 4.0, CPS must be able to fulfill their purpose to a large extent without intervention of human users [2]. According to the Society of Automotive Engineers (SAE) taxonomy for autonomous driving, we refer to such systems as highly automated or fully automated CPS [2]. Already today and even more so in the future, systems engineering is one of the core competence fields for building such highly automated or fully automated CPS.

In the case of highly automated CPS, it is necessary to have a more comprehensive understanding of the term 'functional safety'. In contrast to the understanding of the term by the ISO 26262 standard, which essentially considers the malfunction of system components, highly automated

CPS require an analysis of the interaction of a) the functionality of the CPS under consideration with b) its context (e.g. other CPS in collaboration). This analysis serves to detect possible safety threats resulting from the interaction between system functions and contextual conditions, such as the interaction between the autonomous driving function of a vehicle and the failure of the signalling system at an automated road intersection. This new understanding of functional analysis, which goes far beyond the requirements of ISO 26262, is the subject of the SOTIF standard [3].

It is important to understand that security threats can also arise from inadequate or non-compliant cyber security. Relevant cyber security standards, such as ISO 21434 [4] in the automotive sector, have recently attempted to take this into account. Corresponding measures to mitigate such security issues then refer to the establishment of appropriate measures and technologies to increase the cyber security of the CPS to an adequate level. It becomes evident that systems engineering research in the CPS field needs to take holistic, tightly integrated approaches for safety and cyber security engineering that consider both the engineering of the CPS and the management of its operation.

These threats to safety must be identified during the development process and mitigated, e.g. by specifying suitable requirements or safety devices (safety monitors) which bring the CPS to a safe state should CPS fail to behave according to requirements or expectations. Since CPS often monitor and control technical or physical processes, control theory is a discipline of great importance in the development of such systems. In this context, the concepts of monitoring and controlling technical/physical processes are reflected in various artefacts of systems engineering. For instance, the requirements originated from the way the processes should be controlled, as well as from decisions made about the design of the necessary sensors and actuators or even about the design of the algorithm for the computational processes of the feedback system.

In order to be able to develop such complex technical systems consisting of software and hardware, seamless systems engineering processes are required, establishing techniques, methods and tools for challenges such as the following examples. Since CPS in many fields of application work together in dynamically formed networks at runtime to pursue higher-level goals, possible collaboration structures must be identified and analysed in requirements engineering. For example, in the development of autonomous vehicles, the collaboration structures in which these vehicles must operate should be taken into account. Examples of such structures might be vehicle convoys to optimize the flow of traffic or at automated intersections to ensure safe crossing of the intersection, even with high traffic volumes and in complex traffic situations. In collaborative CPS, the issue of coordinated decentralized monitoring and control of technical/physical processes is added; an example of this is the coordinated acceleration or deceleration of the various vehicles within a convoy of vehicles.

In the case of highly automated systems, the involvement of the human user is required in (a few) defined situations to ensure that the system is able to fulfil its purpose of ensuring safe operation. The integration of the human user must be effective, i.e. the user interface of these systems must be designed in such a way that the human user is able to perform the necessary tasks according to the intention, as free from errors as possible and within the existing time restrictions. One might think here of the example of autonomous road traffic, where highly

automated systems require the driver to take control of the vehicle when a critical driving situation occurs.

Enabling-technology domains

Internet of Things (IoT)

The Internet of Things community developed around the goal of providing a means for all devices to be globally connected via the internet. The name 'Internet of Things' was used in 1999 by Kevin Ashton during a presentation to his higher management at Procter & Gamble. He described IoT as a technology that connected several devices with the help of RFID tags (radio frequency identification) for supply-chain management [5]. In 2008 the first international conference on IoT took place in Switzerland, discussing RFID, short-range wireless communications, and sensor networks; today, these topics continue to represent the major technological research domain for advancing the IoT, gathering information about the real world that can then be made useful in some way [6].

Since 2010 it has been normal for many different devices to be in our homes to be connected to the internet. Connected devices are used extensively in the consumer domain. In 2015, to support advancement of IoT for industry, the European Commission created the Alliance for Internet of Things Innovation (AIOTI). Applying IoT to the industrial environment has been termed industrial IoT, or IIoT, and has the goal of optimizing production value while considering the many additional challenges related to safety, security and performance. IIoT technologies support interconnectivity with the internet in the context of these challenges, enabling not only networked smart objects and information technologies but also "optional cloud or edge computing platforms, which enable real-time, intelligent, and autonomous access, collection, analysis, communications, and exchange of process, product and/or service information, within the industrial environment" [7]. IoT technologies, in particular those for the IIoT, will be standard constituent elements of future safety-critical frameworks. IIoT is an enabler for Industry 4.0, which will affect all industries [8]. However, IIoT will only become a reality through the convergence of Operational and Information Technologies (OT & IT), which are currently separated. The convergence of IT and OT will be supported by dependable Edge Computing [9], which is a logical extension from Cloud Computing towards the edge of the network (where machines are located), enabling applications that demand guarantees in safety, security, and real-time behaviour.

Enabling the infrastructure to support distributed intelligence and information exchange is at the core of IoT, so supporting cross-community work on CPS decentralization, decomposability and human interaction is important. These are already areas receiving some focus from the IoT community [10], [11], as indeed is the case for bringing communities around an embedded computing backbone, with work considering edge-cloud computing [12] exchanges. As an enabling technology, IoT responds to support other domains which means its focus changes based on the latest domain challenges, corroborated in recent IoT roadmapping activities that its landscape is changeable in nature [13].

Artificial intelligence (AI)

The Artificial Intelligence (AI) community plays a crucial role in the development and operation of cyber-physical systems (CPS). AI technologies, such as machine learning, deep learning, and reinforcement learning, are now being deployed operationally to enhance the capabilities, autonomy, and adaptability of CPS across sectors including transport, healthcare, and manufacturing. With the entry into force of the EU AI Act and its staged implementation through 2027, AI in safety-critical CPS has moved from a research challenge to an operational and regulatory reality. This demands close collaboration between the AI community, CPS engineers, domain experts, safety practitioners, and regulatory bodies to ensure that AI-enabled CPS satisfy both functional safety requirements and AI-specific compliance obligations. Industry discourse increasingly frames these capabilities under the banner of "Physical AI" or "Embodied AI," referring to AI systems that perceive, reason, and act in physical environments; however, the challenges of bridging digital AI and physical-world constraints in CPS demand domain-specific integration rather than simple extension of general-purpose models [<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S2452414X25002614>]

A primary concern is the shift from abstract "trustworthiness" to concrete "assurance in operational context." Assurance for AI in CPS must be system-specific and domain-specific, aligned with the certification regimes already governing safety-critical products (e.g., automotive ISO 26262, aviation DO-178C/DO-254, industrial IEC 61508). The AI community is actively developing techniques for explainable AI (XAI), but explainability requirements must now be differentiated by stakeholder. Engineers require technical explanations (feature attribution, gradient analysis) for debugging and validation; operators need actionable rationale for real-time decision support; regulators demand audit trails, model cards, and datasheets as compliance evidence; and end users require appropriately calibrated trust indicators. Projects like SAFEXPLAIN [14] focus on creating explainable deep learning solutions with end-to-end traceability that comply with functional safety requirements while preserving performance; an approach now essential for meeting EU AI Act transparency obligations taking effect from August 2026.

Another key focus area is the robustness and safety of AI systems throughout their operational lifecycle. Researchers are developing methods for adversarial testing, formal verification, and runtime monitoring to ensure that AI systems behave safely and reliably even in the presence of uncertainties and adversarial inputs. Critically, these verification approaches must extend beyond pre-deployment testing to continuous assurance during operation; particularly for AI systems that learn or adapt post-deployment. Runtime safety envelopes, guarded architectures with deterministic fallbacks, and operational design domain (ODD) monitoring are emerging as essential techniques. Collaborations between the AI community and domain experts in safety-critical industries remain crucial for understanding the specific requirements and constraints, and acceptable risk levels of each application domain.

The AI community is also working on addressing the challenges of data quality and bias in AI systems. Ensuring the diversity, representativeness, and integrity of training data is essential for building AI models that perform reliably and equitably in real-world scenarios. Standards

organizations and industry consortia are developing guidelines and best practices for data collection, annotation, and validation in safety-critical applications.

AI change management has emerged as a critical discipline for CPS. Unlike traditional software where updates follow established change control processes, AI systems present unique challenges: model retraining, fine-tuning, and online adaptation can alter system behaviour in ways that invalidate prior safety assurance. The EU AI Act's post-market monitoring requirements (Article 72) and the concept of "significant change" triggering re-assessment create specific obligations for AI-enabled CPS. Controlled lifecycle processes are now essential, incorporating gated approvals before deployment, comprehensive version control linking models to their training data and code, drift detection (both data drift and concept drift), and documented rollback procedures. The AI community is exploring techniques such as lifelong learning, transfer learning, and online adaptation, but these must be reconciled with certification requirements. A key research challenge is enabling AI systems to evolve safely without requiring complete re-certification for each update.

Collaboration between the AI community and other stakeholders, including CPS engineers, domain experts, and regulatory bodies, is essential for the successful integration of AI in safety-critical systems. Joint research initiatives, workshops, and standards development efforts provide platforms for knowledge sharing, best practice development, and the creation of common frameworks and guidelines.

A paradigm shift is underway from assuring AI systems in isolation to assuring human-AI teaming. Regulatory frameworks including the EU AI Act emphasise human oversight requirements, but the challenge extends beyond mere oversight to genuine collaboration between humans and AI components. The European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) has issued preliminary guidance on human factors assurance for AI-based systems, and similar frameworks are emerging across safety-critical domains. Key research questions include: how to test and validate joint human-AI team performance (not just AI accuracy in isolation); how to identify and mitigate failure modes that emerge specifically at human-AI handoff points; how to maintain meaningful human agency as AI autonomy increases; and how to design interfaces that support appropriate trust calibration; neither over-reliance nor under-reliance on AI recommendations. This human-AI teaming perspective must inform the design, validation, and certification of future CPS.

One area where AI can significantly contribute to CPS is in enabling coordinated collaboration among system components and with humans. Multiagent systems [15] provide a paradigm for understanding and building distributed systems where autonomous computational components work together towards common goals. Agent-oriented software engineering methodologies, such as Tropos [16], offer promising approaches for specifying, designing, testing, and delivering CPS from a software engineering perspective. With the emergence of agentic AI architectures and large language model (LLM)-based agents, this coordination challenge is becoming increasingly relevant and increasingly complex from an assurance perspective. Future CPS may involve AI agents that negotiate, delegate, and coordinate autonomously, requiring new approaches to specify acceptable behaviour boundaries, verify emergent system properties, and maintain human oversight over agent collectives.

High-Performance Computing (HPC)

High-performance Computing (HPC) consists of the aggregation of powerful computing resources for solving problems that require large computing power¹⁴. Recently, HPC technologies were only required in the context of traditional massively parallel “number crunching” applications like weather prediction, computational chemistry, or computational fluid dynamics. However, the latest developments in low-power computing technologies [17] – required in the HPC industry to scale performance levels further – has facilitated the adoption of HPC technologies in a wide range of CPS applications.

Existing HPC platforms offer the computation capabilities needed by the most demanding CPS applications within an affordable power budget in domains such as automotive, space, avionics, robotics and factory automation. Centralized domain architectures that replace the traditional federated computing architectures – like those required by economically affordable autonomous driving systems – are only possible when HPC technologies are deployed. Single-chip high-performance embedded computing platforms reduce the traffic flow through CPS’ electronic networks and enable high-speed communication as required for processing vast amounts of information in real time. So this community will be important for consolidating the embedded computing backbone.

Furthermore, these technologies involve parallel processing, that is, splitting the tasks up into parts for several computers (or multiple cores) to process, thus reducing the time taken to complete tasks. This characteristic thus holds a direct relation with the CPS challenges of decomposability and decentralization – how tasks can be split up while ensuring safety and security for people, the system and its environment.

Unfortunately, the deployment of HPC in a CPS increases the complexity of the resulting system and may have non-negligible impact on the verification and validation costs of relevant system properties (e.g. safety and security). Thus, an effective exploitation of HPC technologies in cyber-physical applications requires at least either the development of new methodologies to verify and validate such complex systems or the adaptation of key technologies to the specific context, as explored in the EU-funded PROXIMA¹⁵ and MASTECS¹⁶ projects, for example.

Big Data

Big Data is foundational to CPS where practices are evolving to better align with safety, reliability, and accountability requirements. This is because cyber-physical systems (CPS) increasingly rely on continuous, multi-modal data from cyber, physical, and social domains, combined with analytics that must be both low-latency and trustworthy. Risk-aware, explainable, and privacy-

¹⁴"High Performance Computing," European Commission, Online: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/high-performance-computing>. [Accessed 26 Nov. 2023].

¹⁵ "Probabilistic real-time control of mixed-criticality multicore and manycore systems (PROXIMA)," Online: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/611085>. [Accessed 25 Mar. 2026].

¹⁶ "MASTECS: Multicore Analysis Service and Tools for Embedded Critical Systems," Online: <https://masteecs-project.eu/>. [Accessed 25 Mar. 2026].

preserving approaches are being adopted across the data and AI lifecycle, guided by frameworks such as the NIST AI Risk Management Framework and ISO/IEC 23894^{17 18}.

Architecturally, CPS are shifting from cloud-centric data pipelines toward an edge–cloud continuum to process latency-sensitive data closer to their sources while retaining cloud-scale capabilities. ETSI Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) specifications support this shift by standardizing application enablement, discovery, and federation, enabling interoperable analytics execution across operators and domains [18].

Real-time CPS operation increasingly depends on event-driven data architectures. High-throughput streaming platforms enable continuous ingestion and routing of unbounded data streams, while stateful stream-processing frameworks provide event-time semantics and strong processing guarantees. Together, these capabilities support online control loops and anomaly detection at millisecond timescales^{19 20}.

Interoperability at the information layer is a critical enabler for CPS. Standardized device and asset descriptions allow heterogeneous components to expose machine-readable interfaces that analytics services can discover and use consistently. In industrial contexts, standardized digital representations of assets support data exchange across organizational boundaries. At ecosystem scale, data-space architectures provide policy-aware connectors and governance mechanisms for sovereign, cross-company data sharing, particularly when CPS data traverses supply chains and critical infrastructure^{21 22 23}.

For hard real-time communication, deterministic data exchange is increasingly supported by industrial publish–subscribe mechanisms combined with time-sensitive networking. These approaches can meet strict latency and jitter requirements using traffic shaping and time-aware scheduling, even on commodity hardware [19]. Trust and privacy are treated as first-class

¹⁷ NIST. Artificial Intelligence Risk Management Framework (AI RMF 1.0), Jan. 26, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.6028/NIST.AI.100-1>. [Accessed 25 Mar. 2026]

¹⁸ ISO/IEC 23894:2023. Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Guidance on risk management. International Organization for Standardization, 2023. <https://www.iso.org/standard/77304.html>. [Accessed 25 Mar. 2026]

¹⁹ Apache Kafka. Introduction: event streaming and platform capabilities. <https://kafka.apache.org/intro/>. [Accessed 25 Mar. 2026]

²⁰ Apache Flink. Stateful Stream Processing (concepts; exactly-once via checkpoints). <https://nightlies.apache.org/flink/flink-docs-master/docs/concepts/stateful-stream-processing/>. [Accessed 25 Mar. 2026]

²¹ W3C. Web of Things (WoT) 1.1: Architecture, Thing Description, Discovery — W3C Recommendations, Dec. 5, 2023. <https://www.w3.org/press-releases/2023/enhanced-web-of-things-connects-diverse-iiot-ecosystems/>. [Accessed 25 Mar. 2026]

²² Industrial Digital Twin Association (IDTA). Asset Administration Shell Specification — Part 1: Metamodel Schema, 2023. https://industrialdigitaltwin.org/en/wp-content/uploads/sites/2/2023/06/IDTA-01001-3-0_SpecificationAssetAdministrationShell_Part1_Metamodel.pdf. [Accessed 25 Mar. 2026]

²³ International Data Spaces Association (IDSA). Reference Architecture — IDS-RAM (v4). <https://internationaldataspaces.org/offers/reference-architecture/>. [Accessed 25 Mar. 2026]

concerns: differential privacy provides formal guarantees for analytics on sensitive data, while standardized provenance models enable end-to-end traceability, auditability, and explainability in multi-party CPS deployments²⁴ [20]. These mechanisms help operationalize international risk-management frameworks and support compliance with regulatory instruments such as the EU AI Act²⁵.

Sustainability considerations further shape Big Data architectures for CPS. Energy- and resource-efficient edge analytics reduce data movement while supporting low-latency operation. Techniques such as model compression and quantization enable on-device inference, and specialized edge accelerators improve energy efficiency under tight thermal and cost constraints [57, 58]. Overall, Big Data for CPS is evolving toward stream-first, edge-native, interoperable, and trustworthy architectures, with ongoing challenges in semantic integration, decentralized data management, and robust operation across heterogeneous and distributed environments.

System of systems

The “System of Systems” (SoS) concept has been around for at least fifty years, but in the last twenty it has been an area of major concern. Following the description of its characteristics by Maier [21]; it is defined in ISO15228 as: “SoS...brings together a set of systems for a task that none of the systems can accomplish on its own. Each constituent system keeps its own management, goals, and resources while coordinating within the SoS and adapting to meet SoS goals”²⁶. As for CPS, SoS represents a type of application, which can be the same, e.g. railway systems, as well as a technology domain - where the focuses are different.

Broadly, one can consider SoS applications as independent systems that interoperate (work together) to achieve a purpose, with a significant amount of ubiquitous networking. In the case where they have extensive software control between safety-critical systems, the application itself is both a SoS and a CPS because they share common characteristics. Figure 3 describes the relationship between SoS, CPS, and the Internet of Things. Where infrastructure interactions are supported by internet protocol, then the CPS is also described as IoT, which is necessarily always a SoS. There are also interesting SoS-CPS applications that interact through means other than the internet protocol (e.g. mechanical or electromagnetic

Figure 3: Technology relations of SoS, IoT, and CPS [22].

²⁴ W3C. PROV-DM: The PROV Data Model (Recommendation), 2013. <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-dm/>. [Accessed 25 Mar. 2026]

²⁵ EPRS (European Parliament Research Service). AI Act implementation timeline (OJEU publication July 12, 2024; staged application 2025–2027), June 2025. https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/ATAG/2025/772906/EPRS_ATA%282025%29772906_EN.pdf.

²⁶ "ISO/IEC/IEEE 15288:2023 Systems and software engineering — System life cycle processes," 2023. Online:<https://www.iso.org/standard/81702.html>. [Accessed 25 Mar. 2026].

interactions) and the engineer may need to guard against such interactions for safety or performance reasons.

However, from the technology perspective, CPS application research considers how all technology communities are integrated to create a system and its interactions, with the SoS technology community contributing to the coordinated collaboration aspect. This is a key property for future CPS, meaning that SoS research is indispensable for creating future CPS. In relation to embedded computing, the importance of localized processing, while maintaining a connection to centralized processing capacity, is recognized as a priority in areas such as edge computing, which uses SoS technology. This also links directly with the challenge of decentralization or decomposability where systems work together. A smart city is an example of human interaction and SoS, for example; it manages busy traffic at city junctions to minimize delays for drivers and pedestrians.

In 2012, INCOSE conducted a survey to identify “pain points” for SoS practitioners, i.e., the problems that kept systems engineers and managers awake at night [23]. The study indicated seven main areas of concern: SoS authorities; leadership; constituent systems; capabilities and requirements; autonomy, interdependencies and emergence; testing, validation and learning; and SoS principles. It is no coincidence that creating CPS includes these pain points, because they are concerned with networked, intelligent systems of high complexity. This suggests that the communities of SoS and CPS as research fields have areas of common interest suitable for collaboration. SoS technology is considered an essential element within the final CPS [24].

Digital Twins and the Metaverse

Digital twins are a global phenomenon, the target of major investment and the subject of countless projects and publications. Part of their appeal is the simplicity of the concept, at least to those of us who have grown comfortable with digital, virtual worlds. The term “Digital Twin” was coined by Grieves and Vickers to describe a concept that arose in their work on managing product life cycles. There is extensive, diverse and rapidly growing literature on digital twins, alongside a burgeoning market for the technology. In 2018, digital twin technology was at the top of the Gartner Group’s hype cycle²⁷ and in 2019 it was identified as one of the 10 most strategically important technologies²⁸, and in 2022 they predicted²⁹ that the digital twin market would reach \$183 billion in revenue by 2031. Realising the full potential of digital twins is more of a challenge than it might at first seem. The engineering of digital twins requires a systems engineering approach including different kinds of models in order to provide predictive capabilities. In order to keep down the costs of establishing digital twins, different frameworks automating parts of the elements are promoted e.g. the Digital Twin as a Service [25] and the Abstract Administration Shell [26].

²⁷ See <https://tinyurl.com/yc86c53v>.

²⁸ See <https://tinyurl.com/y5wkfewe>.

²⁹ See www.gartner.com/en/documents/4011590.

Human-CPS interaction will also advance with the advent of “metaverse” technologies [27], in particular when CPS operate in close proximity or hand-in-hand with human operators. The metaverse will provide haptic feedback over robots that complement and advance human capabilities [28]. Human operators will receive visual guidance in their view of augmented reality, and will obtain the ability to project themselves into the CPS they control. They will sense, act and interact through the impersonated system with other humans and with the environment in which the CPS operates. They will receive extended cognition and operating capabilities over swarms, receive recommendations from concurrently running AI subsystems, and manage the complexity of CPS hierarchies with ample application areas. Human caretakers may intervene in case of emergency or when service robots hit the boundaries of autonomy. At the same time, the fact that the environments surrounding a CPS are very diverse and unpredictable, will require that they also be incorporated in these virtual representations. Any kind of CPS autonomy risking damage to people or goods in the surroundings must be accounted for from a trustworthiness perspective [28]. This is investigated, for instance, in the RoboSAPIENS project³⁰. All over the world research projects on increasing autonomy using digital twins are started up, e.g. DT-CORE³¹. The research needed to ensure that digital twins will live up to their promises have been outlined [29].

Swarms will act in harsh environments on Earth, in space and on remote celestial bodies instead of exposing humans to the risks they have to take today. Examples include mining, nuclear-waste handling and reactor deconstruction, but also asteroid mining and exploration. Replacing the internet with a network of immersive virtual worlds, cyber-physical systems will allow the metaverse to bridge into reality, with all the benefits, but also all privacy, safety and security risks this entails.

Digital twinning is one of the enabling technologies for exercising such advanced control from the digital realm over the real, physical world. Digital twins are virtual models of reality that are continually updated about the actual state of their physical counterparts and which can enable decision-making that, in turn, leads to changes in the real world. The long-term goal of digital twins is to be able to capture the intentions and objectives of the physical twin, but also to improve overall performance through digital simulation, testing and monitoring how the real-world physical system should act in its environment [30]. While the aim is to advance into a better future, this can threaten safety and security when not handled with utmost care. Thus, it will be inevitable for the metaverse and digital-twin communities to join forces with the CPS community to achieve real-time safe, secure, and cyber-attack resilient automation from the moment metaverse-enlightened CPS are designed and throughout their lifetime.

Production-environment influencer domains

Members of the production-environment domain communities are responsible for the industrial product process and lifecycle. This includes enterprise policy and processes, decisions about technology usage and the evolving physical plant [31]. They drive the large-scale production of

³⁰ See <https://robosapiens-eu.tech/>

³¹ <https://digit.au.dk/research-projects/dt-core>

goods using equipment in the form of modular automated product lines. Such equipment typically combines mechanical, electrical, and software components; it also requires substantial initial investment and maintenance costs. Throughout its long lifecycle (15-30 years) [31], the equipment operator and component suppliers cooperate to repair and repurpose/upgrade parts at a minimal cost. This imposes several constraints on component models and their versions, which in turn constraints policy and process management.

In addition, the arrival of digitalization and the CPS revolution brings the “servitization in manufacturing” opportunity, a paradigm shift where manufacturers shift to offer product-related services, beyond just selling a tangible asset (For further discussion of this concept and examples, see the article “Everything as a service” in this HiPEAC Vision). In the above example of automated product lines, component providers could offer monitoring, online maintenance, repair, and overhaul services [32] among other value-added services. Service contracts generate more steady revenue compared to the cyclical product business, but, in general, organizations in manufacturing struggle to drive servitization [32], because the introduction of the new services incurs higher costs without proportional returns.

The adoption of digitalization tools and solutions and the development of innovative services leveraging the full potential of CPS require incentives and coordinated efforts among different partners. Research projects, partnerships in which early movers and less-digital companies cooperate to embrace servitization and adopt CPS tools, provide a nurturing environment, where decision-makers find that the “test-before-invest” concept is an incentive that helps lower barriers and can evaluate potential benefits. For example, in the H2020 HUBCAP [33] project, less digitally focused SMEs were able to pair up with model-based design providers to adopt digital innovation and enhance their solutions using model-based design technology.

Figure 4: Snapshot from the Sandbox showing SME asset.

Among the success stories, there is the example of the partnership between Mototok International GmbH, a provider of innovative aircraft tug solutions, and Evitado Technologies GmbH, a provider of LiDAR-based algorithms adding advances from the self-driving car industry to an already innovative CPS product. Other examples show how advances were made in training for industry 4.0, the development of innovative organ preservation devices in the medical domain, smart textiles, and precision agriculture.

The prime innovative aspect of HUBCAP is a web-based collaboration platform that facilitates stakeholders’ access to computing resources and advanced CPS design and engineering solutions, by providing a cloud-based sandbox solution (Figure 4). The sandbox provides pre-installed models and tools, allowing companies to experiment with new tools and assets in a ready-to-use virtual machine available via a regular web browser, with emphasis on performance and interaction between partners. This is taken forward and combined with DevOps capabilities, also in a digital twin as a service (DTaaS) setting [25].

Production-environment community members are deeply involved with the cross-community challenges identified. There is a historical synergy with the development and advancement of embedded computing, which will continue in the future. This community is always demanding advancements in embedded computing, and advances in manufacturing also affect how we produce the embedded platforms of the future. Regarding decentralization and decomposability, there are several lessons learned and case studies in which cooperation and adaptation to local and greener processes promote research, discussion, and changes to manufacturing. Finally, this community has a particular interest in the challenge of physical collaboration with people. This interest is from both an internal perspective, covering topics such as human-machine interaction and collaborative robots, and an external perspective, where the potential for improvement from product usage data needs to be fully explored.

Market-influencer domains (society needs, regulation, standards, policy)

CPS are believed to have an enormous impact on many aspects of socio-economic life. Therefore, a number of stakeholders grouped here under the generic name of ‘market influencers’ will have a stake in shaping the future of CPS and of the contributing domain communities.

Societal needs may be described basically by means of individuals or groups putting forward requirements and benefitting from CPS. The individual appears here as the consumer who is, in one way or another, making use of either a product incorporating CPS, or elements of larger CPS implementations, addressing communities of end users in terms of mobility, personal life (general wellbeing), healthcare, leisure, environment, etc. Other needs may be identified in the area of public services offered at local and national government level, including education, healthcare services, community services, and operation of public institutions.

As well as responding to societal needs, however, CPS also pose new challenges. Some specific fields include education and employment, as CPS induce the obsolescence of certain professions and create new ones. Therefore education, including training and retraining will be affected, as will the employability of the existing and future workforce, which will have implications for the labour market and social security.

Regulation – both hard and soft legislation - will have to be adapted in order to govern CPS so as to ensure their smooth integration into society. However, given the rapid cross-border spread of CPS technology, international agreements might be needed, too, particularly if we consider the globalized nature of today’s value chains. Regulation will have to address the interplay between CPS actors (producers, consumers) as well the foreseen and unforeseen effects of the technology. Regulation is also supposed to be structured according to the societal needs that the technology is supposed to fulfill. A particular aspect of related regulation might address the human individual, chiefly in relation to human-machine interaction, which is anticipated to increase significantly in the coming years (intruding into both privacy and healthcare). The “must be implemented” regulation should be supplemented with recommendation-type measures of indicative nature.

Standards ensure interoperability and compatibility of products from different producers and allow the market presence of a large number of actors. Moreover, standards are important in

order to set and describe safety levels and quality frameworks. To some extent, standards provide the technical base for legislation governing the area and also give room to innovation as usually standard specifications can be fulfilled in a variety of competing ways.

Policy aims to achieve certain results in a given field by reflecting society's needs or goals. Public policy in particular is directed towards supporting certain areas through frameworks of development in terms of tax incentives, grants or even regulation. Policy also includes public investment in facilities or processes of general interest. A further aspect for consideration is policies aiming to increase employment in a differential manner within the given population (i.e. in favour of disadvantaged groups), or to ensure development of regions lagging behind. Such policies also set out to address issues of general interest like climate change (that can only be done at international level) or the environment.

Beyond public policy, one should take into consideration policies of generically named "groups of interest". Pressure groups such as non-governmental organizations (NGOs) consumer associations also have policies for their vision and procedures to support their realization, which can indirectly influence the market.

These "market influencer" stakeholders between them represent the conditions under which all the other domain communities operate for producing future CPS. The relevance of their involvement should be apparent, especially when considering the aggregative effects of contributing and cross-domain technologies. Deficits in education in one domain community can have a knock-on effect on other communities. Training approaches and certification can be a deciding factor in the sustainability of mixed-domain technologies. Policy can evolve approaches and perspectives that enhance behaviours supporting longer-term governance or culture, providing resilience, value generation and trust in new technologies.

Conclusion

With respect to coordinating CPS research as an application domain, additional approaches and orchestration will need to be introduced. This is because the application-domain perspective is based on the product side, with cumulative effects being considered through the aggregation of layered technology contributions from the contributing stakeholder domain communities. Another issue is that disruptive discoveries, technologies or developments might influence the cycle of research. For example, if significant progress is made on quantum computing, or discoveries in material/biological science, that could make sensors more different.

Orchestration of research is particularly about knowledge management, longer development cycles, persistence and refinement of multi-disciplinary approaches for collaboration between communities. Take the example of constructing a building where a new team takes over every few months. Limited progress can be made without guidance at a higher level. This is similar for advancing CPS research. Persistence of acquired interaction techniques, between project collaborations, is significantly more difficult to maintain. For instance, usability and sensor experts have specific languages for their domains.

Therefore, approaches that support collaborations and tailored during the work should be taken, refined, and applied in subsequent collaborations of different groups. A dedicated CPS research instrument could advance this concept, in conjunction with future CPS support action projects. Projects themselves will also need to provide environments with favourable conditions for integrated research across knowledge domains, considering the multi-dimensional challenges, with conditions significantly different to those for developing component technologies.

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